

THE PROBLEM OF TRANSLATING PROPER NAMES IN A LITERARY WORK*Z. Fayzulloyeva¹**Abstract:*

A literary text is considered to be a completely separate element of the general literary environment due to the presence of a large number of unique characteristics. This also explains the numerous problems associated with translating such literary works. One of the most important problems of this kind is the subject of this work which is the translation of proper names as the main functional component in the structure of a literary text.

Key words: proper names, lexical units, realia, transcription, toponyms, fiction

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In modern linguistics, proper names are often defined as naming lexical units, in contrast to common nouns, which are considered denoting units. In other words, the main function of the proper names is nominative, intended to distinguish objects of the same type [Superanskaya, 1973: 153].

A.V. Superanskaya in her classification relies on various Russian and foreign linguists of the 20th century. It defines the proper names into several categories, but the most important of them, in our opinion, is the classification of names in connection with named objects. According to her, the approach to division into sectors can be different due to not only objective, but also subjective reasons which are determined by factors of social order and the individuality of the researcher” [Superanskaya, 1973: 173].

A. V. Superanskaya takes as a basis the classification of A. Bach (1952) in her research. A. Bach divided proper names into several types.

1. The names of living beings or creatures considered to be alive.
2. The names of things, which include areas, houses, vehicles, works of fine art, names of astrographic and cosmic objects.
3. The names of institutions, societies.
4. The names of such actions as dances and games.
5. The names of thoughts, literary works, military and other plans.
6. The names of musical motifs and works. [Bach, 1952: 4]

Another important aspect in studying proper names is their relation to the reality. Realia as an important concept in linguistics and translation studies has not yet been recorded in dictionaries. However, many linguists have been studying this issue for a long time, and today a number of definitions have been given. The definition of S. Vlahov and S. Florin seems to us the most concise: “Realities are words and phrases naming objects that are characteristics of the life of one nation and alien to another. Having national and historical features they, as a rule, do not have exact correspondences (equivalents) in other

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languages, and, therefore, cannot be translated on a general basis, requiring a special approach" [Vlahov, Florin, 1980 :47]

Onomastics is a separate branch in the study of realities or non-equivalent vocabulary. Proper names are an integral part of any culture, reflecting many aspects of the life of a particular nation. A.V. Superanskaya says the following about the proper names "The specificity of the subject being studied is that it is linguistic at its core, it also includes ethnographic, historical, geographical, sociological, literary components" [Superanskaya, 1973: 7].

Fiction conveys the historical, linguistic, ethnographic and many other features of the culture to which the author of the work belongs, and is also a reflection of the personality of the author and his thoughts. A separate and important element of any work of art is the proper name (names of characters, names of settlements, localities, names of organizations). All this serves to give the work a certain flavor, depending on the author's intention.

Transcription, according to most translation theorists, is the priority way of translating proper names and toponyms. This is a phonemic likening of a word sounding in the original language to a new word formed in the translation text [Aleksyeva, 2004: 220]. Transcription is characterized by certain rules for transferring personal names from the original language to the target language, which include changing the order of first and last names in accordance with Russian tradition, formatting complex first and last names using a hyphen, as well as changing the ending of foreign names.

Toponyms undergo approximately the same transformations with the only difference that complex toponyms can be transmitted either through a hyphen (New- York) or without it (Hampton Court). The most detailed scheme for translating proper names according to the principle of phonetic similarity is presented by D. I. Yermolovich, describing the correspondence of each English sound to Russian [Yermolovich, 2001: 135].

Thus, a proper name is a serious translation problem in most of its manifestations and requires a thorough approach both during pre-translation analysis and directly during translation.

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